

Lidar Deployment Acceleration by Researches in Japan (LiDAR in Japan)

Jun Tanemoto
Shimizu Corporation

LiDAR Installation Status in Japan

- Total number of wind LiDAR installation in Japan

- Ground based Lidar: approx. 450
- Nacelle mounted Lidar: approx. 5
- Scanning Lidar: approx. 100
- Floating Lidar: approx. 10

Based on an interview with a LiDAR provider A

Transition of LiDAR use (provided by LiDAR provider B)

Ground Based LiDAR

- Total number of installation: approx. 450
- Use case
 - Mostly resource and/or site suitability assessment (including repowering project) together with 60m height met mast
 - ✓ Recent projects utilize LiDAR data in complex terrain with proper CDF correction and validation
 - Data filling for scanning LiDAR measurement, wake measurement research etc.
- Regulation changed
 - Before October 2022
 - ✓ 60m or higher met mast had been considered as tall building.
 - ✓ Approval of Minister of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism were required for the design/construction (i.e. hurdle such as certification existed)
 - After October 2022
 - ✓ The requirement has been relaxed up to below 90m height
- Any effect on LiDAR deployment?
 - Demand has not changed
 - 60m met mast + LiDAR
 - ✓ have cost advantages (90m met mast needs aircraft warning light (i.e. need extra power supply))
 - ✓ are less occupation area

Based on an interview with a LiDAR providers, wind farm developers

Floating LiDAR

- Total number of installation: approx. 10
- Use case
 - Mostly research, such as validation of FLS itself or mesoscale model etc.
- Why few?
 - Still developing near shore (~5km)
 - Need accurate TI
- Outlook
 - Next phase (5~10km off from coast) might be competition of FLS and long-range scanning LiDAR
 - Further future projects need Floating LiDAR

NEDO Project at Mutsu Ogawara test site

Cited from Uchiyama et.al. (2024, 2025)
Also presented at Task 52 lunch seminar series (2025)

Scanning LiDAR

- Total number of installation: approx. 100
- Use case
 - Resource/Site condition assessment for offshore wind project
 - Wake measurement
- Why so many?
 - Most of offshore wind projects are near shore (~5km) so far
 - Installation and O&M hurdles are lower than floating LiDAR
 - We care turbulence. Dual use enable to measure TI

Scanning LiDAR matched recent industry's demand

Cited from Yoshimura (2022), presented at Task 52 kick-off meeting

Cited from Shimada et.al. (2022)
Also presented at Task 44 and 52 joint workshop (2024)

10-year Researches of Scanning LiDAR in Japan

Number of presentations for scanning LiDAR topics in domestic wind energy conference

Year	Topics								Total
	Validation	Data correction, post process etc.	Sensitivity test / Uncertainty	Monitoring	Wind characteristics (horizontal/vertical distribution, boundary layer etc.)	Inflow/wake measurement	Use of validation for numerical simulation	Project/guidelines introduction literature review etc.	
2015							1		1
2016					1				1
2017									0
2018	1								1
2019	2								2
2020	2							2	4
2021	4	1			1		3		9
2022	2	2					3	2	9
2023	4		2	2			2		10
2024	1	1	1			5	2		10
Total	16	4	3	2	2	5	11	4	47

Note

Cited from Tanemoto et. al. (2025), Journal of JWEA(in Japanese)

2019: NEDO offshore wind measurement project launched

2022: NEDO offshore wind measurement test site project launched

2023: NEDO offshore wind measurement guidebook 1st edition issued

2023: NEDO wake measurement project launched

2024: Mutsu Ogawara test site operation started

Scanning LiDAR matched recent industry's demand + evidenced by many researches

Key Challenges and Recent Moves

- Wind measurement for non near shore project
 - We still care turbulence
 - ✓ 5~10km off coast
 - Underestimation of TI measurement by scanning Lidar with long probe length
 - Low data availability (trade off of TI measurement accuracy)
 - ✓ 10km off coast
 - Ultra long-range LiDAR: lack of specification to satisfy (wind energy) industry requirement
 - Floating LiDAR: Accuracy of TI measurement, data filling
- New NEDO offshore measurement project
 - Started on June 2025
 - Focuses on far shore wind measurement
 - ✓ TI correction of FLS
 - ✓ Survey of needs of direct measurement (met mast etc.) and its rational method
 - ✓ Update of NEDO guidelines, including far shore etc.

Based on interviews with developer,
consultant, LiDAR provider

- What researches need for future?
 - Ground based LiDAR
 - ✓ TI correction in complex terrain (wishing complete project without met mast)
 - ✓ Stand-alone power system/Low energy consumption LiDAR
 - ✓ Improve of data availability in heavy snow/icing conditions
 - Nacelle mounted LiDAR
 - ✓ Technical guidelines (recommended probe length etc.)
 - Scanning LiDAR
 - ✓ Energy yield uncertainty estimation without white-box validation, conversion method from LoS to Horizontal wind speed
 - ✓ Expansion of measurement range
 - Improvement of data availability 3km or far distance (target: 70-80%)
 - Accurate TI measurement/correction with long probe length (10% underestimate 100m probe length, 20% 200m?)
 - Understanding of systematic relations of probe lengths and magnitudes of TI underestimations (validation with different probe lengths (50, 100, 200m) and multiple site)
 - Floating LiDAR
 - ✓ TI correction
 - Found hope by recent researches
 - Need more validations with various metocean conditions
 - ✓ Data filling (expect no other reference measurement available near a FLS)
 - Others
 - ✓ Expert consensus of optimal choice of LiDAR for offshore wind measurement (i.e. conditions when we can/cannot use scanning/floating LiDAR)
 - ✓ High quality noise/interference filtering method
 - ✓ Expand use case of LiDAR (e.g. gust measurement during construction)
 - Outlook
 - ✓ Market expand due to further offshore project development, demand of 2D/3D measurement, farm level AEP/load optimization

Conclusions

- LiDAR in Japan
 - Many ground based LiDARs and scanning LiDARs has been deployed.
 - Scanning LiDAR deployment is one of the success story by synergy of industry demands and research outcomes
- Research needs and future challenges
 - Topics has been addressing in Task 52 (complex terrain, cold climate)
 - Development of confident wind measurement method for non nearshore project. (Keywords: TI, data availability/filling)

Acknowledgement

This presentation contents are mostly obtained by interviews with LiDAR providers, developers, consultants in Japan. I would like to thank their kind cooperation.